

Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils

Project 'CarboSeq'

Deliverable 4.3

Reporting guidelines for Tier 2-SOC- sequestration / country together with WP 8

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ABSTRACT

Emission factors for European grasslands focussing in Germany and the UK.

WP4. Grassland management

DELIVERABLE - WP4.3. Reporting guidelines for Tier 2-SOC-sequestration / country together with WP 8

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1. Introduction

The estimated SOC-stock changes of grasslands will feed into the estimation of the SOC-sequestration potential based on IPCC-Tier 2. This document reports on the development/setup of emission factor which have been calculated for grassland systems in Europe in response to changes in key two drivers:

- (1) land-use change and
- (2) land management practices and change.

The methodology used is described in Deliverable 4.2 and includes details regarding the long-term experiment dataset (for dataset details see DL 4.1) and the equation used (for detail see DL 4.2).

The emission factors (EFs) are to be used by WP8 (Building Scenarios for C Sequestration) to assess the C sequestration potential using the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) Tier 2 approach (emission factor x activity data) (IPCC, 2019).

2. Results

2. 1. Emission factor -Overview

Emission factors (EFs) were calculated from long-term grassland experiments in seven European countries. There were a total of **258 data values** of EFs which corresponds to 258 unique treatments from all of the experiments. The overall mean EF value was 1.15, the minimum was 0.435, the maximum was 2.57 and the standard deviation was 0.277. A summary of the EFs with specific treatments given in Table 1. The results are split into the two main groups:

Land management

- (i) permanent grasslands (no change in land use over decades) and having received a “Nutrient **Management**” (fertilisation, see DL 4.1) and

Land use change

- (ii) grasslands established following a **land-use change from cropland** (control crop)
- (iii) grassland receiving a **silvo-pastoral systems** established from existing grassland (control grassland having not trees).
- (iv) forests experiencing a **land use change to agroforestry with grass** (control forest having no grass).

The treatment effects and mean value for each treatment shows that there were no overall effects of land use or management. For a comparison of the specific land use types a significant effect was detected ($P = 0.03$). Three different type of management (control, mineral fertiliser and farmyard manure/ slurry) were found to be significantly different. In Appendix 1 a table of emission factors is given for all studies evaluated from the LTE dataset.

Table 1. A summary of the simulated mean emission factor values (EFs) values for selected land use and management measures from long-term grassland experiments in Europe

Treatment group	Treatment	n	Emission factor	SE	P values
1	Land use (No) & Management (Yes)	197	1.16	0.02	0.60
1	Land use (Yes) & Management (No)	61	1.14	0.05	
2 ^a	Arable control	19	0.96	0.04	0.001
2 ^a	Grass	17	1.37	0.11	
2 ^a	Agroforestry	21	1.19	0.07	
2 ^a	Wood	3	0.77	0.08	
3 ^b	Remaining Grass (Control)	9	1.13	0.03	0.015
3 ^b	Mineral fertiliser grass	175	1.14	0.02	
3 ^b	Farmyard manure/ slurry grass	13	1.34	0.03	

^aThis group of treatments is for experiments where there was a Land use change or difference in land use

^bThis group of treatments is for experiments where there were Nutrient Management treatments tested

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2. 2. Emission factors by country and soil order

Table 2 provides the mean emission factors for the seven countries evaluated.

Table 2. A summary of the mean emission factor values (EFs) for different countries based on long-term grassland experiments in Europe

Countries	n	Emission factor	SE
France	16	1.25	0.09
Germany	45	1.09	0.05
Netherlands	8	1.26	0.05
Spain	2	0.922	0.13
Sweden	1	1.26	NA
Switzerland	9	1.05	0.02
UK	177	0.435	0.26

Table 3 provides the mean emission factors according to the different WRB soil orders (WRB, 2006).

Table 3. A summary of the mean emission factor values (EFs) for different WRB soil orders from long-term grassland experiments in Europe

WRB soil orders	n	Emission factor	SE
Andosol	1	0.96	NA
Arenosol	2	1.28	0.31
Cambisol	57	1.10	0.04
Fluvisol	9	1.23	0.14
Gleysol	5	1.24	0.08
Haplorthod	3	1.29	0.08

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2. 3. Emission factors for Germany and the United Kingdom

There were sufficient data to evaluate the EFs specific to two countries: Germany and the United Kingdom. Table 4 shows the EFs for the different treatment factors in Germany and also for the United Kingdom in Table 5.

Table 4. A summary of the mean emission factor values (EFs) for selected land use and management measures for grasslands in Germany based on long-term experiments

Treatment group	Treatment	n	Emission factor	SE	P values
1	Land use (No) & Management (Yes)	16	1.03	0.01	0.41
1	Land use (Yes) & Management (No)	29	1.12	0.08	
2 ^a	Arable LUC (control)	17	0.97	0.04	0.01
2 ^a	Grass	11	1.40	0.17	
2 ^a	Wood	1	0.61	NA	
4 ^b	Remaining grass (Control)	19	1.00	0.03	0.13
4 ^b	Mineral fertiliser grass	26	1.16	0.09	

^aThis group of treatments is for experiments where there was a Land use change or difference in land use

^bThis group of treatments is for experiments where there were **Nutrient Management** treatments tested

Table 5. A summary of the mean emission factor values (EFs) for selected land use and management measures for grasslands in the United Kingdom based on long-term experiments

Treatment group	Treatment	n	Emission factor	SE	P values
1	Land use (No) & Management (Yes)	167	1.17	0.02	0.012
1	Land use (Yes) & Management (No)	10	0.96	0.10	
2 ^a	Arable LUC (control)	2	0.82	0.16	
2 ^a	Agroforestry	3	1.03	0.11	0.147
2 ^a	Grass	2	1.37	0.23	
2 ^a	Wood	2	0.85	0.05	
3 ^b	Remaining grass (Control)	9	1.13	0.03	0.039
3 ^b	Mineral fertiliser grass	145	1.16	0.02	
3 ^b	Farmyard manure/ slurry grass	13	1.34	0.03	

^aThis group of treatments is for experiments where there was a land use change or difference in land use

^bThis group of treatments is for experiments where there were Nutrient Management treatments tested

Reporting guidelines for Tier 2-SOC-sequestration / country together with WP 8

2. 4. Emission factors for Cambisols

An evaluation of the Cambisol soil order was undertaken and the EFs are given in Table 6 for that soil order (WRB, 2006).

Table 6. A summary of the mean emission factor values (EFs) for selected land use and management measures for long-term grassland experiments with a Cambisol soil type

Treatment group	Treatment	n	Emission factor	SE	P values
1	Land use (No) & Management (Yes)	30	1.12	0.03	
1	Land use (Yes) & Management (No)	27	1.08	0.08	
2 ^a	Arable LUC (control)	14	0.97	0.06	0.18
2 ^a	agroforestry	1	0.92	NA	
2 ^a	grass	10	1.33	0.18	
2 ^a	wood	1	0.89	NA	
3 ^b	Remaining grass (Control)	1	1.29	NA	0.045
3 ^b	Mineral fertiliser grass	22	1.05	0.02	

^aThis group of treatments is for experiments where there was a land use change or difference in land use

^bThis group of treatments is for experiments where there were Nutrient management treatments tested

2. 5. A comparison between emission factors and potentially environmental and physical explanatory factors

Figure 1. A comparison between emission factors and annual mean rainfall (mm) for long-term grassland experiments in Europe (according to seven European countries)

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Figure 2. A comparison between the emission factor values and annual temperature (°C) for long-term grassland experiments in Europe (according to seven European countries)

Reporting guidelines for Tier 2-SOC-sequestration / country together with WP 8

Figure 3. A comparison between the emission factor values and the content of clay (%) for long-term grassland experiments in Europe (according to seven European countries)

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Figure 4. A comparison between the emission factor values and the content of clay (%) for long-term grassland experiments in Europe (according to seven European countries)

Reporting guidelines for Tier 2-SOC-sequestration / country together with WP 8

Figure 5. A comparison between the emission factor values and mean annual rainfall (mm) for long-term grassland experiments in Europe (according to WRB soil order)

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Figure 6. A comparison between the emission factor values and annual mean temperature (deg. C) for long-term grassland experiments in Europe (according to the different WRB soil orders)

Figure 7. The emission factor values for selected long-term grassland experiments in Europe

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Appendix 1 – Calculated emission fac*tors (EFs) data

Table A1. A list of all the studies evaluated with the calculated emission factors (EFs) and whether the study tested management change (LMC) or land use change (LUC) and the corresponding study type.

Study ID	Country	LMC	LUC	Study type	EF
Bal_1	Switzerland	✓		Grass nutrient	1.08
Bal_2	Switzerland	✓		Grass nutrient	1.03
Bal_3	Switzerland	✓		Grass nutrient	1.09
Frue_1	Switzerland	✓		Grass nutrient	1.02
Frue_2	Switzerland	✓		Grass nutrient	0.96
Frue_3	Switzerland	✓		Grass nutrient	1.05
Hayn_1	Germany	✓		Grass nutrient	1.11
Hayn_3	Germany	✓		Grass nutrient	0.99
Hayn_5	Germany	✓		Grass nutrient	1.01
Hohe_1	Germany	✓		Grass nutrient	1.04
Hohe_3	Germany	✓		Grass nutrient	0.97
Hohe_5	Germany	✓		Grass nutrient	0.98
Hohe_7	Germany	✓		Grass nutrient	1.07
Hohe_9	Germany	✓		Grass nutrient	1.07
Iden_1	Germany	✓		Grass nutrient	1.02
Iden_3	Germany	✓		Grass nutrient	1.02
Iden_5	Germany	✓		Grass nutrient	1.16
Lich_1	Germany	✓		Grass nutrient	0.94
Lich_3	Germany	✓		Grass nutrient	1.04
Lich_5	Germany	✓		Grass nutrient	1.04
Mord_1	Germany	✓		Grass nutrient	1.12
Newc_1	United Kingdom	✓		Grass nutrient	1.28
Newc_2	United Kingdom	✓		Grass nutrient	0.78
Newc_3	United Kingdom	✓		Grass nutrient	1.23
Newc_4	United Kingdom	✓		Grass nutrient	0.89
Newc_5	United Kingdom	✓		Grass nutrient	1.13
Obwb_1	Germany	✓		Grass nutrient	0.97
Oens_1	Switzerland	✓		Grass nutrient	1.06
Slwd_1	United Kingdom	✓		Grass nutrient	1.29
Slwd_10	United Kingdom	✓		Grass nutrient	1.78
Slwd_11	United Kingdom	✓		Grass nutrient	1.24
Slwd_12	United Kingdom	✓		Grass nutrient	1.32
Slwd_13	United Kingdom	✓		Grass nutrient	1.49
Slwd_14	United Kingdom	✓		Grass nutrient	1.73
Slwd_15	United Kingdom	✓		Grass nutrient	1.20
Slwd_16	United Kingdom	✓		Grass nutrient	0.95
Slwd_17	United Kingdom	✓		Grass nutrient	0.98

Reporting guidelines for Tier 2-SOC-sequestration / country together with WP 8

Slwd_18	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	0.88
Slwd_19	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.12
Slwd_2	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.08
Slwd_20	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	0.75
Slwd_21	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	0.78
Slwd_22	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.66
Slwd_23	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.04
Slwd_24	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	0.73
Slwd_25	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.07
Slwd_26	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.02
Slwd_27	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	0.89
Slwd_28	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.25
Slwd_29	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	0.83
Slwd_3	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.34
Slwd_30	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	0.80
Slwd_31	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.12
Slwd_32	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.32
Slwd_33	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.06
Slwd_34	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	0.88
Slwd_35	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.15
Slwd_36	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	0.95
Slwd_37	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.02
Slwd_38	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.22
Slwd_39	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	0.82
Slwd_4	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.70
Slwd_40	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	0.91
Slwd_41	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	0.76
Slwd_42	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.20
Slwd_43	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	0.94
Slwd_44	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	0.97
Slwd_45	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	0.77
Slwd_46	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	0.73
Slwd_47	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	0.98
Slwd_48	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	0.85
Slwd_49	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	0.62
Slwd_5	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.50
Slwd_50	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.45
Slwd_51	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.09
Slwd_52	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.78
Slwd_53	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	0.91
Slwd_54	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.10
Slwd_55	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	0.68
Slwd_56	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	0.77
Slwd_57	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.20
Slwd_58	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.24
Slwd_59	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.01
Slwd_6	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.54

Reporting guidelines for Tier 2-SOC-sequestration / country together with WP 8

Slwd_60	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	0.70
Slwd_61	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	0.84
Slwd_62	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	0.90
Slwd_63	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	0.87
Slwd_64	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	0.92
Slwd_7	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	0.69
Slwd_8	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.33
Slwd_9	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	0.88
Wag2_1	Netherlands	✓	Grass nutrient	1.22
Wag2_3	Netherlands	✓	Grass nutrient	1.29
Wag2_5	Netherlands	✓	Grass nutrient	0.97
Wag2_7	Netherlands	✓	Grass nutrient	1.44
Wag2_9	Netherlands	✓	Grass nutrient	1.27
Watt_1	Switzerland	✓	Grass nutrient	1.14
Watt_2	Switzerland	✓	Grass nutrient	0.98
Hill_1	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.42
Hill_2	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.57
Hill_3	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.33
Hill_4	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.22
Hill_5	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.28
Hill_6	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.28
Hill_7	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.32
Rot1_1	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.09
Rot1_10	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.09
Rot1_11	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.09
Rot1_12	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.00
Rot1_13	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.21
Rot1_14	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.11
Rot1_15	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.15
Rot1_16	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.14
Rot1_17	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.26
Rot1_18	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.12
Rot1_19	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	0.99
Rot1_2	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.07
Rot1_20	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.10
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Rot1_23	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.24
Rot1_24	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.24
Rot1_25	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.36
Rot1_26	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.38
Rot1_27	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.20
Rot1_28	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.11
Rot1_29	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.03
Rot1_3	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.03
Rot1_30	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.09
Rot1_31	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.20

Reporting guidelines for Tier 2-SOC-sequestration / country together with WP 8

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Rot1_39	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.46
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Rot1_41	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.41
Rot1_42	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.32
Rot1_43	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.37
Rot1_44	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.23
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Rot1_47	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.57
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Rot1_54	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.82
Rot1_55	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.35
Rot1_56	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.34
Rot1_57	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.67
Rot1_58	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	2.22
Rot1_6	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.10
Rot1_67	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.32
Rot1_68	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.30
Rot1_69	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.25
Rot1_7	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.06
Rot1_70	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.03
Rot1_71	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.22
Rot1_72	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.20
Rot1_73	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.28
Rot1_74	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.09
Rot1_75	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.17
Rot1_76	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.00
Rot1_77	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.12
Rot1_78	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.00
Rot1_79	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.14
Rot1_8	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.06
Rot1_80	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.08
Rot1_81	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	0.97

Reporting guidelines for Tier 2-SOC-sequestration / country together with WP 8

Rot1_82	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	0.94
Rot1_83	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.16
Rot1_84	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.17
Rot1_85	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.11
Rot1_86	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.25
Rot1_87	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.33
Rot1_88	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.33
Rot1_89	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.02
Rot1_9	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.23
Rot1_90	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.19
Rot1_91	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.35
Rot1_92	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.30
Rot1_93	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.44
Rot1_94	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.30
Rot1_95	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.33
Rot1_96	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.42
Rot1_97	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	1.29
Rot3_2	United Kingdom	✓	Grass nutrient	0.66
Lugo_2	Spain	✓	LUC grass-silvopastoral	1.05
Bed_1	United Kingdom	✓	LUC grass-silvopastoral	0.93
Chat_1	France	✓	LUC crop-agroforestry nutrient	1.05
Chat_2	France	✓	LUC crop-agroforestry nutrient	1.05
Chat_3	France	✓	LUC crop-agroforestry nutrient	1.12
Mell_1	France	✓	LUC crop-agroforestry nutrient	1.08
Mell_2	France	✓	LUC crop-agroforestry nutrient	1.05
Rest_1	France	✓	LUC crop-agroforestry nutrient	1.26
Rest_2	France	✓	LUC crop-agroforestry nutrient	1.05
SJdA_2	France	✓	LUC crop-agroforestry nutrient	1.42
SJdA_3	France	✓	LUC crop-agroforestry nutrient	1.45
Veze_1	France	✓	LUC crop-agroforestry nutrient	1.07
Veze_2	France	✓	LUC crop-agroforestry nutrient	1.06
Bib_1	Germany	✓	LUC crop-grass	0.92
Doss_2	Germany	✓	LUC crop-grass	1.10
Edel_2	Germany	✓	LUC crop-grass	0.88
Eisi_2	Germany	✓	LUC crop-grass	0.98
ErKi_1	Germany	✓	LUC crop-grass	0.92
Grun_1	Germany	✓	LUC crop-grass	0.78
Hech_1	Germany	✓	LUC crop-grass	0.76
Ober_2	Germany	✓	LUC crop-grass	1.03
Oden_2	Germany	✓	LUC crop-grass	0.85
Rotm_2	Germany	✓	LUC crop-grass	0.91
Schy_1	Germany	✓	LUC crop-grass	1.48
Utgb_1	Germany	✓	LUC crop-grass	1.08
Wkhm_1	Germany	✓	LUC crop-grass	1.20

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Reporting guidelines for Tier 2-SOC-sequestration / country together with WP 8

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